

A STUDY ON EMPLOYEE RESISTANCE TOWARDS ORGANISATIONAL CHANGE

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ABSTRACT

Expect changes in this life because nothing is permanent. Changes only serve to improve the world's ability to compete with technology. Because the world is becoming more competitive, everyone wants to accept the changes and adapt. It is also applicable to businesses. These organizational modifications must compete globally because employment has become more varied, complex, and technical. Some people reject change because they have been adopted and are addicted to past things. They suddenly find it difficult to accept the changes, which leads to Resistance. The group wishes to take the required actions to overcome the opposition. Only then will the organization be successful and have a positive change process; from this survey, I have concluded that gender has no significant impact on the adaptability of change, and age has no significant effect on gender

Keywords: Resistance to change, Organizational change, sustainable development, forces for change.

INTRODUCTION

An organization's ability to adapt to change must be developed, or it will be left behind or carried away by the forces of change. Many factors are at work within the organization, making change desirable and unavoidable. Technology, market pressures, and general socioeconomic settings are among these forces. External pressures force internal organizational variables such as machinery, equipment, processes, policies and procedures, structural relationships, etc. "change" refers to any change in an organization's overall work environment. It entails changes to structural linkages and people's roles in an organization. To live and thrive, organizations must interact with their external environment. They take inputs from their surroundings, process them, and return the outputs to the environment. External and internal forces both exert pressure on people to change. Technology, market conditions, social changes, and political parties are examples of external forces.

In contrast, changes in managerial people, operational personnel, and deficiencies in the present structure are examples of internal factors. Change resistance can occasionally show itself at the organizational level. They are defined by functional division of labor, a focus on role prescriptions rather than organizational goals, a focus on hierarchical relationships for coordinating various jobs and connecting as corporate goals, rigid definitions of roles with little flexibility and precise, a significant level of decision-making and vertical communication

centralization, acceptance of existing status classifications, and companies offering similar to the organization and its values. Similar researches have been conducted by many authors (Benita, 2021; Monica, 2021; Kumar, 2020; Kumar & Shree, 2019; Monica & Supriya, 2019; Mahesh & Uma Rani, 2019; Mahesh, Gigi, & Uma Rani, 2019; Robert & Monisha, 2019; Kumar & Shree, 2018).

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Jones, G.R., Gorge, J. M. (2000) has concluded in the Organizational Change: Conflict Management and Leadership Analysis International Journal of Social Science Research, "Employee conflicts are defined as the presence of discord that occurs when different individuals or groups' goals, interests, or values are incompatible and frustrate each other's attempts to achieve organizational objectives."

Kongala Ramprasad (2013) stated, "People who have interactions and have conflicts in main goals, subgoals, and values, and they consider others as an obstacle to reaching their aims," according to the development of an attitude toward change.

Lowder, T.B (2009) states the difference between Organizational Change v/s Organizational Commitment, Change is inevitable, but it isn't always welcome. Resistance to change is natural, and it stems from ingrained habits, a fear of the unknown, conformance to traditionally expected behaviors, ignorance of change's ramifications, and individual variances. He believes that it could lead to conflict or crisis unless carefully handled. Competition for finite resources, status inconsistency, win-lose scenarios, the need for change, confusing regulations, and communication challenges are other reasons for organizational conflict."

Lukman Susanto (2003) has concluded from his study that Maximum organizational changes are wrong but also beneficial. Because many people believe that the last thing management wants throughout a transformation process is Resistance. Resistance has resulted in significant confusion and uncertainty in many cases, potentially turning the shift into a disaster or, worse, dissolving the entire company. Even though many theories are now attempting to respond to those resistances more objectively, many still believe they are harmful.

Robbins (2009) introduced the Developing Change Readiness, "Some kinds of conflict help the organization achieve its goals and increase performance; these are functional, constructive conflicts that benefit the organization."

Rod Farr-Wharton and Yvonne Brunetto's (1995) study helped examine how organizational changes affect interpersonal relationships because the quality of supervisor-service employee relationships impacts individual and corporate outcomes.

Schraeder, Mike (2001) This research study was primarily concerned with organizational commitment. Nothing is possible without the promise, so his research looked at how personal views of business success, job security, and communication connected to corporate obligation in a pre-merger setting to assess potential Resistance to a proposed merger. Individuals highly committed to the company are more likely to support change, whereas those less committed

are more likely to reject it. According to the findings, business success, job stability, and communication are positively associated with organizational commitment.

Tim Wray and Martin R. Fellenz (2007) have stressed the importance of communication. Because communication and organizational transformation are intricately intertwined, official and informal communications were critical at that time. The function of formal and informal communication in organizational development is examined in this research. It identifies and discusses the central processes of sense-giving and individual and social sense-making; For Change communication to transmit and regulate the received message, a more advanced understanding of informal communication and personal and social sense-making processes is required.

Tutsch (2008) has stated in the Journal of Applied Behavioural Science, Challenging Resistance to Change, "The most lasting trait that convinces humanity that progress and development are reliant on conflicts is conflict." Conflict is commonly viewed as catastrophic, unnatural, dysfunctional, and repulsive, but it can be a forerunner to positive transformation if appropriately managed."

Wayne H. Bovey Andrew Hede (2001) has done a study and found that Individual psychology plays a critical role in changing Resistance. He looks at the psychological aspects that contribute to Resistance to organizational change.

Conceptual Framework

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research uses a descriptive research design to reflect specific top-specific characteristics accurately. Fifty-two individuals were sent a standardized questionnaire and asked to respond; a convenience sampling survey method was used to collect the data from an I.T. company in Chennai, was chosen as the study's sample. To support the research, references from various journals, literature, books, and publications related to the issue were consulted.

Research Objectives:

To study the employee resistance attitude towards organizational change.

To find out various factors that become a cause for the Resistance.

To find out multiple areas where the difference is required.

Research Design:

The descriptive and causal research designs were employed in this study. Descriptive research studies focus on characterizing the features of a single person or a group of people. The workers of the company make up the number of my research.

Sample Size: The selected features include a sample, which is a technical term. We used 52 employees from the overall population sample size to perform the analysis.

Questionnaire: The researcher has designed a questionnaire taking Absenteeism, New policies, and Technical change factors as independent variables and Employee resistance as a dependent variable. The questionnaire comprised 28 questions, including 6 demographic questions.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Gender-Wise Distribution

Table 1: Frequency of gender-wise distribution

S. No	Gender	Frequency	Percent
1	Male	32	61.5
2	Female	20	38.5
	Total	52	100.0

Interpretation: From the above table, it been noticed that 61.5% are male and 38.5 are female.

Age-Wise Classification

Table 2: Frequency of age-wise distribution

S. No	Interval	Frequency	Percent
1	Below 25	12	23.1
2	25-35	24	46.2
3	35-45	13	25.0
4	45-55	2	3.8
5	Above 55	1	1.9
	Total	52	100.0

Interpretation: The table shows the age of the respondents 23.1% are below 25 years of age group, 46.2% are in the age group of 25-35, 25.0% are in the age group of 35-45, 3.8% are in the age group of 45-55, and 1.9% are above 55 years of age group.

Experience of Respondents

Table 3: Frequency of Experience

S. No	Interval	Frequency	Percent
1	Below 2	11	21.2
2	2-5	21	40.4
3	5-8	16	30.8
4	8-11	3	5.8
5	above 11	1	1.9
	Total	52	100.0

Interpretation: The above table shows the Experience of the respondents 21.2% have experienced below two years, 40.4% have 2-3 years of Experience, 16% have Experience of 5-8 years, 5.8% have Experience of 8-11 years, and 1.9% have experienced more than 11 years.

Educational Qualification

Table 4: Frequency of educational qualification

S. No	Qualification	Frequency	Percent
1	Diploma	1	1.9
2	U.G	38	73.1
3	P.G	9	17.3
4	Others	4	7.7
	Total	52	100.0

Interpretation: The above table shows the educational qualification of the respondents 1.9% are Diploma graduates, 73.1% are UG graduates, 17.3% are PG graduates, and 7.7% have chosen others as their educational qualification.

Organizational Change

Table 5: Mean analysis of organizational change

S. No	Organisational Change	N	Mean	Rank
1	Changes are essential	52	4.42	1
2	Changes are primarily negative in nature	52	3.90	2
3	Willing to be adapted with any changes	52	3.42	3
4	Organization does not plan accordingly to the change	52	2.79	4

Interpretation: The above table shows the mean analysis of employee's opinion on employee resistance towards organisational change. Majority of the employees believe that the changes are essential in my organisation and this takes the first rank with the highest mean value of 4.42. The response on primarily negative in nature scores second place with the mean value of 3.90. I'm willing to be adapted with any changes in the organisation statement takes 3rd rank with the mean value of 3.90. The statement organisation does not plan accordingly to the change they happen and ranks 4th with the mean of 2.79

Absenteeism

Table 6: Mean analysis of absenteeism

S. No	Absenteeism	N	Mean	Rank
1	Change in the way of dealing with absenteeism	52	3.21	1
2	Happy with the present absenteeism policy	52	2.94	2
3	Organization follows proper ways to reduce absenteeism	52	2.62	3

Interpretation: The above table shows the mean analysis of employee's opinion on employee resistance towards organisational change. Majority of the employees believe that there should be a change in the way of dealing with absenteeism and this takes the first rank with the highest mean value of 3.21. The response on the present absenteeism policy in the organisation scores second place with the mean value of 2.94. The organisation follows proper ways to reduce absenteeism statement takes 3rd rank with the mean value of 2.62.

Table 7: Mean analysis of new policies and technical change

S. No		N	Mean	Rank
1	New policies are well informed by all the employees	52	3.87	1
2	Some technical changes are required in my organization	52	3.44	2
3	Willing to accept new policy implementation	52	3.33	3
4	Usually get training if any technical changes implemented	52	3.27	4

Interpretation: The above table shows the mean analysis of employee's opinion on employee resistance towards organisational change. Majority of the employees believe that new policies are well informed by all the employees and takes the first rank with the highest mean value of 3.87. The response on they feel some technical changes are required in my organization has ranked second with the mean value of 3.44. The statement I am willing to accept new policy implementation takes 3rd rank with mean value of 3.33. I usually get training if any technical changes have been implemented statement ranks 4th with the mean of 3.27.

Table 8: Mean analysis of employee resistance distribution of respondents

S. No	Employee Resistance	N	Mean	Rank
1	Changes in the organization generate opportunities for personal growth	52	3.46	1
2	Lack of information about processes of change generates misunderstandings in the organization	52	3.33	2
3	People are afraid because of the uncertainty generated by the new way of working	52	3.29	3
4	Change involves the need for more detailed knowledge of the way things work	52	3.04	4
5	People develop mechanisms for not changing	52	3.04	5
6	The different attempts at change in this organization continue to be unsatisfactory	52	3.00	6
7	Organizations implement changes against the employee resistance	52	3.00	7
8	Change generates opportunities for employees who know how to take advantage of it	52	2.94	8
9	People are slow to adapt to the new elements introduced by change	52	2.65	9
10	Not becoming involved with the processes of change is a common practice in this organization	52	2.48	10

Interpretation: The above table shows the mean analysis of employee's opinion on employee resistance towards organisational change. Majority of the employees believe that Changes in the organization generate opportunities for personal growth and takes first rank with the highest mean value of 3.46. The response on lack of information about processes of change generates misunderstandings in the organization has scored second with the mean value of 3.33. The statement people are afraid because of the uncertainty generated by the new way of working takes 3rd rank with the mean value of 3.29. The statement change involves the need for more detailed knowledge of the way things work takes 4th rank with the mean value of 3.04. The response on people develops mechanisms for not changing has ranked 5th with the mean value of 3.04. The different attempts at change in this organization continue to be unsatisfactory statement has ranked 6th with the mean value of 3.00. The statement organizations implement changes against the employee resistance has ranked 7th with the mean value of 2.65. The response on change generates opportunities for employees who know how to take advantage of it has ranked 8th and with the mean value of 2.94. The statement people are slow to adapt to the new elements introduced by change has ranked 9th with the mean value of 2.65. The response on not becoming involved with the processes of change is a common practice in this organization ranked 10th with the mean value of 2.48.

SUGGESTION:

Management should improve the organization's performance and participate in decision-making. As the organization needs a new balance, individuals must overcome their Resistance

to change. Forces of change rely on and must interact with their external environment to exist and grow. The organization should increase awareness before making any changes to deal with employees. Employees feel that implementing modifications will benefit the corporation rather than the general public. The organization should have the financial resources to train change agents and reward those who support the change.

CONCLUSION:

The social structure of an organization's purpose is to achieve balance. Through achieving balance, people learn to anticipate various ecological interactions within their environment. Change Resistance in the workplace is nothing new. The success of significant organizational change is usually determined by how skilfully Resistance is managed. Organizations must analyse, work, and overcome employee resistance while fostering an environment that encourages employees to be "change ready." Look for ways to strengthen the organizational structure that supports its goals.

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